

INTER-INSTITUTIONS COLLABORATION MODEL IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF LAMONGAN NORTH COASTAL WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT

Heny Fajriyah Novianti

**Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, University of Bondowoso, Bondowoso,
Indonesia**
heny@unibo.ac.id

Abstract

Recently the role of woman increase not only the domestic sector but also extend to the public sector. Bases on this idea the government has issued apolicy of coastal community program that known as PEMP (Program Ekonomi Masyarakat Pesisir/ Coastal Community Economic Program). To achieve this goal PEMP issued a series of programs such as swamitra mina, Kedai pesisir (Coastal Shop), KUB dan BLM. At this time the research focussed on KUB and BLM. This study aims to describe the process of institutional collaboration, as well as to explain the structure and role of each others in the process of empowerment. The results showed that the empowerment model of woman in Lamongan coastal community implemented by the existing community institutions there are; the government has the function of identification and assessment as well as region technical organizer. For the identification and assessment function, the government in collaboration with HNSI while for assistance activities the government in collaboration with educational institution (Staidra and APS), for KUB Tunas Samudera TPD was commissioned by staidra institution. The process of empowerment with different TPD cause different output. KUB Tunas Samudera is exelled in entrepreneurship skills while KUB Putri Samudra is superior in koperasi management.

Keywords: *BLM collaboration; empowerment; institution; KUB; PEMP*

A. Introduction

Currently Indonesia has experienced several fundamental changes in terms of the direction of development. One of these changes is the shift in the political map from what was originally centralized to a decentralized political system (regional autonomy). Regarding of this, there has also been a paradigm shift in fisheries resource management from state poverty, towards community-based fisheries resource management (PSBK or CBFRM/community Base Fisheries resources Management). This conception is expected to provide a channel for aspirations and broad participation space for resource-using communities (Syafa'at, 2006: 38).

Through a new paradigm of community empowerment, they are given the right to manage resources in order to carry out development. The presence of this paradigm takes the initiative to change conditions by providing opportunities for the poor to plan and implement the development programs they have determined. Besides that, the poor are also given the

opportunity to manage their own funds, both from the government and those from other parties. This is what distinguishes between community participation and community empowerment.

Community empowerment is closely related to the creation of job opportunities and business opportunities that provide adequate income for the community. Every member of society is expected to be involved in the development process, have equal opportunities and act rationally. In the development process, the importance of community participation, including women's groups, is an urgent need.

The socio-economic conditions of fishing communities in rural Indonesia have not experienced a significant increase since the end of the New Order era. As stated by Dr. Sudirman Saad (2005) as the Director of Coastal Community Empowerment said that coastal communities inhabit 8,090 villages which are estimated to total 16.42 million people. This community is relatively behind in other words, there are still approximately 28% of the population classified as poor (www.dkp.or.id). Poverty and social inequality that occur in fishing communities are predominantly caused by (Mubyarto, 1984):

1. The negative impact of fisheries modernization policies
2. There are fluctuations in the fishing season
3. Limited capability of fishing technology and conservation of fish products
4. Marketing networks that harm fishermen as producers
5. Unequal profit sharing system

One of the actors who are always in poverty and always increasing in number besides fishermen are women. The conditions of poverty that they experience encourage coastal women to try and work as much as possible to fulfill their daily needs by being willing to work anything in order to make money, including allowing their children to earn an income. Besides that, the Cesscent Team (2003) also noted that women's groups were also creative in creating traditional institutions, such as forming study groups, savings and loans and social gatherings. This institution can be used as a more effective means of empowering women and society at large.

The advantages of women's position are sufficient reasons for a program to involve more women in it. Programs that do not include women mean ignoring the interests of society at large. The current government has responded well to the urgent need for the role of women in development, namely with the existence of a gender mainstreaming policy. Based on presidential instructions (INPRES) no 9 of 2000. The policy requires the State to become mandatory for gender mainstreaming obligations. The main focus of the strategy in this policy is the State. The participation of the government, in this case the State, is by intervening in

every development policy or program that is made so that it always takes gender welfare into account.

PEMP is a policy product of the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries in the form of capital assistance specifically for coastal communities. PEMP is intended as a form of coordination effort to create new jobs, improve rural infrastructure, and participation of poor families and women (DKP Kabupaten Lamongan). PEMP is implemented in almost all areas of coastal communities in Indonesia, including those in the Brondong and Paciran areas. In these two areas, in addition to capital assistance, PEMP organizes several development programs for women in the form of training or in the form of capital loans and capital assistance such as KUB (Joint Business Groups).

The Joint Business Group (KUB) is government assistance provided to residents as a stimulus for the residents' economic activities. Based on the decision of the Lamongan Regent No. 188/238 A/Kep/413.013/2008 regarding the establishment of a marine and fisheries joint business group in Lamongan district, among others; 1) Mackerel Makmur 2) Layang Karya 3) Tonang Mina 4) Madani Bahari 5) Oceanic Shoots 6) Crab Cultivation 7) Mackerel and 8) Cob. In addition to the above, there is one KUB that has been formed since 2005 named Putri Samudera and Tunas Samudera. Furthermore, these two KUB will become the focus of a study entitled " INTER-INSTITUTIONS COLLABORATION MODEL IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF LAMONGAN NORTH COASTAL WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT"

B. Methods

The research location is centered in the Brondong and Paciran sub-districts, especially in Kranji and Tunggul villages in Lamongan district. In these two villages there are Joint Business Groups managed by coastal women, namely Tunas Samudera in Kranji Village and Putri Samudera in Tunggul Village.

This research is descriptive qualitative which can be interpreted as an attempt to investigate a problem by describing the current state of the object of research. For this reason, the data collected must be given meaning, by not just presenting descriptive data (Nawawi: 1996; 75).

The object of this research is all components of the fishing community that are in contact with institutions that collaborate in community empowerment. The institutions involved are the Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Service of Lamongan Regency, members of

the HNSI in this case are the heads of Nelayan Associations in various villages in Paciran and Brondong Districts, members who are members of the KUB (Joint Business Group).

The technique for determining informants used snowball sampling, namely determining informants based on previous informants. Then starting from informants who have received the KUB program in the field, then looking for further informants based on notifications from previous informants, and so on until complete and saturated data is obtained about empowering women in coastal communities from related institutions.

C. Results and Discussion

Denzim in Yuswadi (2005) collected data both in the form of observations, in-depth interviews, in the form of answers or expressions, responsive behavior, then typification and interpretation were carried out to produce an abstract formulation. Therefore, the analysis in qualitative research is circular (continuous throughout the implementation of the research) to test the accuracy of the data, data triangulation and investigator triangulation can be carried out.

MODEL OF INTER-AGENCY COLLABORATION IN LAMONGAN REGENCY

As an effort to prevent this policy from being misdirected or misused, DKP Lamongan limits BLM (Community Direct Assistance) recipients only to types of businesses that have joined a group called Group Business Together or hereinafter shortened to KUB. Meanwhile, as the Community Direct Aid Team, the government gives authority to HNSI assisted by the village government.

In the empowerment process, each institution has a portion of activities according to its function and competence. Institutions that collaborate in coastal women's empowerment activities in Lamongan district include; 1) Regional Government of DKP Lamongan 2) HNSI 3) STADRA

1. DKP Regional Government

The Regional Government (Pemda) through the Marine Fisheries and Animal Husbandry Office of Lamongan Regency, whose duties are 1) operationally responsible for forming and establishing joint business groups (KUB) as potential recipients of community direct assistance; 2) dissemination and Publication of Disbursement of Community Direct Assistance at the district level 4) carry out monitoring and evaluation as well as reporting

The role of the Government in the New Governance paradigm is :

- 1). Leadership,

- 2). Directing
- 3). Empowering
- 4). Facilitating
- 5). Collaborating
- 6). Persuasion and
- 7). Negotiating.

In carrying out its authority, it is hoped that the government will not prioritize orders (direction) but rather by building partnerships and networking.

By coordinating the Lamongan Regional Government has carried out the distribution of authority as a form of regional autonomy. Besides that, by involving several institutions in the community, the local government has involved the community in implementing policies.

2. HNSI

The Indonesian Fishermen Association is a government organization that has often become a government partner in coordinating between the government and the people. In the eyes of the people and the government, HNSI is a facilitator for the people. The organization tries to fight for the rights of fishermen and aims to improve the welfare of fishermen. In each fishing village, HNSI has a sub-organization called Nelayan Association.

In relation to KUB HNSI represented by RN, it has an important role in making adequate and accountable recommendations. The recommendations will then be taken into consideration by the government in providing assistance. In addition to providing coordination, RNs also have a moral responsibility to monitor KUB aid recipients. Monitoring referred to here is simply conducting supervision without intervention. This is done to increase the independence of the target group so that they can be empowered and more independent.

3. STAIDRA

As the target group in the empowerment program, KUB has a companion called the Village Assistance Team (TPD). For the KUB Putri Samudera in the village of Tunggul, the TPD in charge was directly from the Regional Government of DKP Lamongan, while the TPD from Tunas Samudera was a team from STAIDRA.

Staidra is a High School located in Kranji Village. As a tertiary institution, Staidra has a high commitment to community service. Staidra sees that there is still a lot of potential in Kranji Village that has not been fully utilized. With the enthusiasm to make changes

for the surrounding community, Staidra tries to bridge the potential of Kranji Village by submitting a proposal to the local government to develop the surrounding environment. In line with her commitment to the surrounding environment, Staidra is happy to invite mothers in the surrounding environment to participate in the activities she is undertaking.

These activities include creating discussion groups that are held once a month. KUB members are people around them who already have businesses, both on a small and medium scale. In this discussion activity, mothers are given the right to determine the theme that will be used as material for discussion and then Staidra will help find competent parties in their fields to then carry out joint discussions.

Besides that, if necessary, Staidra will intervene in the form of financial management if necessary.

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN FISHERMEN SOCIETY; DOMESTIC AND PUBLIC SECTORS

Judging from the role of Lamongan coastal women above, they can be categorized as women and development. This is based on the phenomenon of woman and development. This is based on the phenomenon of almost equal opportunities with men. For the local community, women who work to make ends meet have become part of their lives. The access that coastal women have is equal to that of men, but their motivation to work is still solely "helping" men in earning a living. This view is not simply released from the teachings they profess. Where the obligation and responsibility to make a living in a family is a man.

Business Group with Tunas Samudera

One of the KUB members is Mrs. Asrifah. He has a business selling packaged rice. In a day he managed to sell about 100 packs of rice. Not only sold in Kranji village, but also to neighboring villages such as Tunggul and Banjaranyar. In 2007 Mrs. Asrifah received capital assistance from the KUB program with various facilities, including ease of repayment and no interest on loans. This system is very useful for small traders like him.

Another member of KUB Tunas Samudra is Bu Saroh. He owns a grocery store business in the Kranji market. Besides the shop business, he also has a LERES cracker business. This business is run together with her husband and mother. While running this business, the biggest difficulty for Bus Sarih was finding employees who fit the criteria. Difficulty building trust and low performance are the main reasons for today's employees. With the KUB program, the difficulties were a little unraveled because there was a discussion and lecture program there, Mrs. Saroh met a lot of people so it was difficult to find employees who fit the criteria.

Putri Samudera Business group

This business group is located in the village of Tunggu Paciran Lamongan. This KUB has been formed since 2005. There are 5 business groups including the smoking group, the smoking group, cracker making, food manufacturing and the fresh fish selling group.

While this program has been running, there have been two trainings, namely cooperative management training by the Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Office and training on making crackers and nuggets from APS (Sidoarjo Fisheries Academy). Besides the training program, there is also capital loan assistance provided to members. So far only the capital loan program is still ongoing. The training for making fish nuggets held by APS is difficult to sell to the public, because the process is relatively long and the selling price cannot compete with similar products that are widely circulated in the market.

Unlike the case with KUB Tunas Samudera, the development of the savings and loan cooperative is still ongoing today. Relatively KUB members have the responsibility to return the loan money. For its members, if they are responsible for returning it, it means that one day if they or other members need a loan, it can still be done. They are well aware that the capital owned by the cooperative must be run in a trustworthy and responsible manner.

D. Conclusion

The results of the research show that the model of women's empowerment in the Lamongan coastal community is carried out by various parties, but the reality shows that there is no synchronization between institutions. Conditions on the ground show the following facts: the government has the functions of identification and evaluation as well as regional technical organizers. The government's identification and assessment function collaborates with HNSI, while in the assistance process the government collaborates with educational institutions (Staidra and APS). For KUB Tunas Samudera the designated accompanying agency is Staidra. In the process of empowering staidra more emphasis on self-development of the target group. For KUB Putri Samudera with TPD directly led by DKP. The empowerment process is more emphasized on the skills and management of cooperatives. Empowerment processes with different focuses lead to outputs; 1) KUB Tunas Smudera is superior in entrepreneurial skills, while 2) Putri Samudera is superior in cooperative management.

E. References

Mubyarto, Dkk. 1984. *Nelayan dan Kemiskinan*. CV Rajawali. Jakarta

- Syafaat, Rahmad. 2006. *Advokasi dan Pilihan Penyelesaian Sengketa; Latar Belakang, Konsep dan Implementasinya*. Agritek YPN Malang.
- Saad, Sudirman. 2005. *Pengembangan Jaringan Ekonomi Masyarakat Pesisir: Upaya Mencapai tujuan MDGs*. Humans Direktorat Jenderal Kelautan, Pesisir dan Pulau-pulau Kecil. www.dkp.or.id diakses pada 18 April 2008 pada pukul 11.19.WIB
- Tim Crescent. 2003. *Menuju Masyarakat Mandiri; Pengembangan Model Sistem Keterjaminan Sosial*. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Yuswadi, Hary. 2005. *Metode Penelitian Sosial dan Humaniora. Suatu Komparansi Pendekatan Kualitatif*. Buku Materi Kuliah. Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik.